

D3.1 Blueprint architecture for PID provider service integrations in a PID-based knowledge graph

Frederik Springer and Markus Stocker

28 November 2025

Imprint

Authored by	Frederik Springer (https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5379-0059), Markus Stocker (https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5492-3212)
Contributions by	Stephanie Hagemann-Wilholt (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0474-2410)
Date of publication	28 November 2025
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734216
License	This work is licensed under https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Deliverable	D3.1 Blueprint architecture for PID provider service integrations in a PID-based knowledge graph

About

PID4NFDI (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through Base4NFDI.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI. DFG Grant Number: [521453681](#)

Abstract

The aim of the Work Package 3 of the PID4NFDI integration phase is to improve access to PID-referenced information. A particular focus lies on research objects for which PID registration is still emerging, as this is where the integration in scholarly infrastructures is least advanced. Specifically, Task 3.1 is about the integration of research instruments in PID-based knowledge graphs as a prototype for other emerging PID resource types. To this end, we developed a dedicated solution fulfilling the need for a comprehensive integration of the instrument data from both PID providers ePIC (B2INST) and DataCite into a single platform. Our federated search tool queries key metafields of instrument records via the B2INST and DataCite APIs, harmonises the results across PID providers, and provides export options for the unified data. The results set can be further explored within the statistics section of this tool, as interactive line graphs and frequency tables illustrate the distributions for different metadata fields. For every instrument record that is connected via related identifiers with other scientific researches these connections are visualised within connection graphs. Still, we are in ongoing discussion with providers of PID-knowledge graphs DataCite and OpenAIRE about the full integration of instrument records across PID providers.

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BESSY	Berliner Elektronenspeicherring-Gesellschaft für Synchrotronstrahlung
CSV	comma-separated values
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ePIC	Persistent Identifier Consortium for eResearch
EUDAT	European research data management and storage service
FZJ	Jülich Research Centre
GFZ	Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum
HZB	Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (German National Research Data Infrastructure)
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OSF	Open Science Foundation
PID	persistent identifier
PIDINST	Persistent Identification of Instruments Working Group
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SMS	Sensor Management System
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

Contents

Introduction	1
Challenges to instrument PID integration	2
Federated search tool as our approach	3
Design implications derived from use cases	4
Core functionalities of the federated search tool	5
Conclusion	10

Introduction

PID4NFDI is an initiative within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI – Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur). Its goal is to create a sustainable and interoperable framework for persistent identifiers (PIDs), enabling discoverability, citability, and interlinking of research outputs across the NFDI consortia. This includes the promotion of PIDs for research objects for which PID registration is still emerging. Alongside material samples, highly granular datasets, projects, and awards, this includes research instruments. According to our recent survey “PID Service Landscape in the NFDI”¹, instruments are among the resource types for which the largest share of surveyed infrastructure managers in the NFDI plan to register PIDs (or, in some cases, already do so).

This positive resonance aligns with the numerous benefits of assigning PIDs to instruments and complementing them with high-quality metadata: Unique identifiers facilitate the interlinking of instruments and datasets, making their role in data generation visible. Rich metadata and the use of related identifiers enable researchers to reproduce the specific instrument configurations used in previous studies, thereby supporting reproducibility. PIDs also make it possible to monitor instrument usage and demonstrate their scientific return on investment, thus potentially informing funding decisions regarding these often costly devices.²

Two PID providers already register PIDs for instruments. These are DataCite and ePIC; the latter of which provides ePIC PIDs for use in the EUDAT B2INST service. The specifics of the PID implementation were heavily influenced by the [PIDINST working group](#), endorsed by the RDA and a key actor in establishing standards for instrument PIDs. Its members studied several use cases to determine the necessary properties for describing instruments across the different scientific domains.³ The resulting PIDINST metadata schema⁴ has been fully implemented with B2INST and is partially mapped to DataCite. DataCite explicitly refers its users to this mapping when filling out metadata fields for instrument records.⁵

¹ El-Gebali and Böhm (2025: 62).

² Take Mayernik et al. (2024: 7f.) as an exemplary journal article discussing the benefits in more detail.

³ Stocker et al. (2020).

⁴ Krahl et al. (2022).

⁵ Stathis et al. (2024).

Architecture for PID provider service integrations in a knowledge graph

Above the framework for PID registration, however, instruments remain largely absent from the scholarly infrastructures. Hence, for example, de Castro et al.⁶ emphasise the need for a timely and coordinated integration effort to fully realise the potential inherent in instrument PIDs. Within Task 3.1, PID4NFDI therefore aims to establish a solution to make instruments registered via both PID providers discoverable through a single interface. While integration with existing infrastructures, such as DataCite Commons, is desirable for a number of reasons (e.g., efficiency and sustainability), technical and organisational challenges still need to be overcome. These are discussed in the following sections, together with possible solutions. This includes a section on how our experiences with the use case partners of PID4NFDI shaped our approach to the problem.

In this report, we address this gap by presenting a blueprint architecture for integrating all instrument PIDs within existing infrastructures such as the DataCite PID Graph. In addition to such a unified platform for discovering instruments and their metadata, Task 3.1 also includes the two sub-tasks of use case reports and guidance on linking instruments with other resources. These separately published outputs closely connect to D3.1 and are referenced throughout.

Challenges to instrument PID integration

The integration of instrument PIDs into well-established knowledge graphs is highly desirable. It would raise awareness of the fact that instruments have become part of the PID landscape, which should encourage the registration and citation of PIDs for instruments. We therefore explored three options for instrument integration: the [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#), the PID Graph with its Web Interface [DataCite Commons](#), and [OpenAlex](#).

The OpenAIRE Research Graph combines data from several PID providers like ORCID, Crossref and DataCite. However, whether DataCite records are considered depends on the “resourceTypeGeneral” value (e.g., dataset, project, or instrument). Instruments are among those entities currently excluded, as they are not regarded as research products or outputs. PID4NFDI is in ongoing discussions with OpenAIRE regarding the potential integration.

The DataCite PID Graph, with DataCite Commons as its web interface, is another knowledge graph that combines resources from multiple PID providers. While it

⁶ De Castro et al. (2023).

already represents instrument records stemming from Datacite, there are insufficient dedicated resources for technical enhancements within the PID4NFDI timeframe. The long-term roadmap for further integration of resources, including a potential inclusion of B2INST, remains unclear.

The OpenAlex codebase has recently undergone a substantial overhaul. With the beta launch on 1 October 2025, most DataCite records became available, and the full production release is scheduled for November 2025.⁷ One of the main objectives of the redesigned OpenAlex system is to simplify the addition of new data sources, which may enable the integration of B2INST in the future. Regarding the newly added DataCite records, some resource types – primarily representing emerging PID categories such as instruments – are currently grouped under the generic category “other,” which is not ideal for raising awareness or enabling targeted retrieval. On the positive side, OpenAlex enriches the metadata with automatically assigned topics embedded within a hierarchical taxonomy of subfields, fields, and domains.⁸ This enrichment constitutes a welcome addition for the instrument records, as the PIDINST metadata schema does not provide dedicated properties for such disciplinary information.

To conclude, OpenAIRE does not feature instruments at all and DataCite Commons and OpenAlex do not consider B2INST yet. Therefore, none of these infrastructures can currently function as a comprehensive, umbrella-level discovery tool for instruments, necessitating an alternative approach.

Federated search tool as our approach

In response to these challenges, we have developed a prototype for a federated search tool, accessible via <https://search.pidinst.org> and through the [PID4NFDI website](#). At its core, it provides a web-based search interface that queries both the [DataCite REST API](#) and the [EUDAT B2INST HTTP REST API](#), combining results retrieved from the two PID providers. The federated search tool performs `GET` requests to the following endpoints: `/dois` at DataCite and `/records` at B2INST. For DataCite, results are filtered by `resource-type-id=instrument` to retrieve only instrument records, whereas all B2INST entries are inherently instruments, so no additional filtering is required. The full metadata for each instrument

⁷ Gould and Demes (2025).

⁸ OpenAlex (2025).

(`attributes` in DataCite, `metadata` in B2INST) are retrieved and stored by the tool, making them available for later use, such as downloads or further analysis.⁹

Design implications derived from use cases

Before presenting how we implemented the idea of a federated search tool in detail, we will share the key takeaways from our collaboration with two PID4NFDI use case partners. It is important background information, as these experiences had a significant influence on the development of the tool. Both [use case reports](#) are available at the homepage of PID4NFDI and at Zenodo.¹⁰

Firstly, we are collaborating with the Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie (HZB, [view all instruments](#)). DataCite DOIs have been registered here for the BESSY II (synchrotron radiation source) and BER II (neutron source) beamlines and experiment stations. These instrument records exemplify how metadata fields should ideally be filled out to comply with the DataCite mapping of the PIDINST metadata schema. Studying them helped us deepen our understanding of the mapping, and it influenced our decision on which metadata fields to index and present in the result list. Specifically, our consideration of DataCite fields that are not represented in the PIDINST metadata schema – and therefore not applicable to B2INST – is based on the purposeful usage of subjects and the resource type here.

The adoption of PIDs for instruments at HZB was motivated by the need to specify the relationship between instruments and other research entities. The use case demonstrates how the different components of large, custom-built devices can be mutually interlinked and connected to their data outputs. When designing the graphical interface for the relationships between PID-identified resources as part of the federated search tool, we prioritised relationships specified through related identifiers for its first version, bearing this in mind.

Our second use case is the Sensor Management System (SMS, [view all instruments](#)), developed by several Helmholtz centers, namely Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum (GFZ), Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), and Jülich Research Centre (FSJ). It is an open-source platform for managing sensors, measurement setups, and campaigns. The properties that describe the devices in the different instances of the SMS include the metadata fields specified by the PIDINST metadata schema. This allows the B2INST extension

⁹ Please refer to our dedicated [GitLab repository](#) to see the codebase of this Flask app.

¹⁰ Böhm (2025), Springer (2025).

to automatically map the properties, which eliminates the need for redundant data input, when registering PIDs via the API or the web interface. The seamless integration of PIDs for instruments undoubtedly contributes to the fact that most of the instruments registered with ePIC are devices featured at one of the SMS instances.

Again, this use case had an influence on the decision which metafields to index and show in the short instrument record profiles on the results page of the instrument search tool. Model and measured variables are no mandatory fields in the PIDINST metadata schema, and are neither at the top of the list of elements the PIDINST use case partners initially considered the most important attributes to describe instruments.¹¹ However, for the Earth & Environment Research Field of the Helmholtz Association the dedicated instrument-specific metadata fields, specially mentioning model and measured variables, were one of the arguments why they opted for the usage of B2INST within the SMS as opposed to DataCite. Recognising the importance of these attributes for a key B2INST user, we included them as searchable fields.

In addition to this, the SMS can be considered a role model in terms of the high priority it gives to data curation. The community-driven development and usage of controlled vocabulary plays a critical part here. We acknowledge this within the presentation of search results by providing favicons that link to the corresponding entries in the [catalogue](#), which describe the specific terms used for instrument type, model, and manufacturer.

These use cases, which highlight actual PID integration workflows with DataCite and B2INST, can contribute to more services, such as equipment databases, implementing support for registering PIDs for instruments. This would populate PID-based knowledge graphs with numerous records containing rich metadata.

Core functionalities of the federated search tool

Any platform that strives to combine data from multiple sources, needs to consider their compatibility. While B2INST fully implements the PIDINST metadata schema, the well-established DataCite metadata schema is more general, designed to accommodate a broad range of resource types. To bridge this gap, the federated search tool utilizes the PIDINST-to-DataCite mapping, enabling results from both

¹¹ See table 2 in Stocker et al. (2020: 5) for the full list.

Architecture for PID provider service integrations in a knowledge graph

providers to be presented through largely harmonized¹² metadata fields. The mapping table is replicated on the index page of the tool to ensure transparency regarding how metadata are aligned. Highlighted cells indicate which fields are indexed for a given query, helping users to understand the coverage of the integrated search results (see Figure 1).

Mapping PIDINST → DataCite

PIDINST (B2INST)	DataCite v4.5
Identifier (M)	Identifier (M)
<i>identifierType (M)</i>	<i>identifierType "DOI" (M)</i>
Name (M)	Title (M)
Owner (M)	Contributor (R) with contributorType: HostingInstitution
<i>ownerName (M)</i>	<i>contributorName (R)</i>
<i>ownerIdentifier (O)</i>	<i>nameIdentifier</i>
<i>ownerIdentifierType (O)</i>	<i>nameIdentifierScheme</i>
Manufacturer (M)	Creator (M)
<i>manufacturerName (M)</i>	<i>creatorName (M)</i>
<i>manufacturerIdentifier (O)</i>	<i>nameIdentifier</i>
<i>manufacturerIdentifierType (O)</i>	<i>nameIdentifierScheme</i>
Model (R)	Description (R) with descriptionType: TechnicalInfo
<i>modelName (R)</i>	
<i>modelIdentifier (O)</i>	
<i>modelIdentifierType (O)</i>	

Figure 1: Integration of the mapping table on search.pidinst.org.

The interface allows for different modes of access. For one, the users can perform free-text queries across key metadata fields. As such, we consider those fields that are mandatory in the PIDINST metadata schema, i.e., identifier, name, and owner, and manufacturer, and most of the recommended fields, i.e, description, instrument type, model name, and measured variables. This is accompanied by subject and resource type which are exclusive to DataCite.

In addition to the free-text search, researchers can look up instruments directly by PID. For DataCite, search by prefix is also possible, which is useful to retrieve all instruments from a given organization. The results are returned in a unified view, which can be sorted, filtered, and exported to files in CSV or JSON format. In

¹² This additionally includes a normalization step that consolidates equivalent values into a consistent form, as the metadata entries often contain variations in spelling or formatting. This process ensures that owners, manufacturers, instrument types, models, or measured variables that are semantically identical but expressed differently are recognized as the same entity. By unifying such entries, the search results become cleaner, more reliable, and more useful for both discovery and subsequent analysis.

Architecture for PID provider service integrations in a knowledge graph

addition to searching for a specific subset, the interface offers the option of displaying all registered instruments. Therefore, the export function can be used to download the entire database as a single harmonized file.

Figure 2: Visualisation of PID registration frequency over time as part of "Statistics" on search.pidinst.org.

Beyond basic retrieval, the interface also provides advanced functionality. A central feature is the ability to generate plots and tables for statistical summaries directly from the search results (see Figure 2). For example, users can obtain frequency tables for instrument type, owner, manufacturer, or measured variables. Generating these for all registered instruments provides an overview of the instrument landscape without leaving the search environment. The generated statistics are not static: users can interactively explore subsets of the data, allowing discovery and analysis to be closely integrated. Filtering the data to refine the analysis for a selected subset is done simply by selecting the respective row label, if only one filter is needed, while multiple filters can be combined by clicking on the needed cells and confirming the selection with enter. For instance, in Figure 3, selecting WET Labs dynamically updates all tables and figures to display only the 72

Architecture for PID provider service integrations in a knowledge graph

instruments produced by this manufacturer, and, alternatively, hitting enter reduces the sample to those instruments produced by Aanderaa or Bosch.¹³

Manufacturer	DataCite (n)	B2INST (n)
Dragino Technology Co., LTD.	0	865
Sea-Bird Scientific	0	163
Stevens Water Monitoring Systems	0	134
KELLER Pressure	0	103
SWAP Instruments	0	88
WET Labs	0	72
Centre for Microscopy, Characterisation & Analysis	67	0
Aanderaa	0	52
Robert Bosch GmbH	0	52

Figure 3: Instrument manufacturer frequency (entries with $n > 50$).

Complementing the interactive search results, we also visualize the interlinking of instruments with other resources. For every instrument record that has related identifiers specified or that is mentioned via its PID as a related identifier in the record of another resource, users can view a connection graph. Each graph represents a single primary instrument and its relationships with other research resources. The graph comprises nodes and edges derived from metadata relating to persistent identifiers. The central node always corresponds to the instrument itself, while the other nodes represent connected resources, such as datasets, journal articles, software or other instruments, via related identifiers. Each node carries basic metadata – title, PID and general resource type – and is visually distinguished by colour according to the resource type. Clicking on a node refers users to the landing page of the respective resource. The edges denote relations between these resources. They are labelled according to the specified relation type (e.g., *IsReferencedBy*, *Cites*, or *IsCollectedBy*), and arrows indicate directionality. Each graph therefore visualises a network centred on a single instrument, illustrating how it is embedded within the broader research landscape – for example, which datasets were produced using the instrument, which publications cite the instrument, and how the instrument connects to other research outputs

¹³ Within attributes, filters are combined via OR, as in the given example for manufacturer, while across attributes the filters are combined via AND. Hence, selecting October 2025 as record creation date in addition to the manufacturers would condense the sample to those instruments produced by Aanderaa or Bosch that were registered in October 2025.

Architecture for PID provider service integrations in a knowledge graph

and infrastructures (see Figure 4 as an example for a connection plot of a well-connected large-scale instrument).

To be able to provide this feature, we perform a daily local harvest of all instrument records and all publications, datasets, or other resources that reference these instruments. Where necessary, we use the [Crossref REST API](#) and the [Open Science Foundation \(OSF\) REST API](#)¹⁴ as additional sources to fill gaps in the data, ensuring that information on titles, DOIs, and general resource types is as complete as possible. This technical set-up – federated search, but local harvesting for visualization purposes – guarantees that the search results are always retrieved from live queries, while information on connections and citation counts is delivered with minimal delay and without the overhead of on-the-fly computation. In this way, the harvesting workflow balances timeliness with efficiency, ensuring a responsive user experience.

Figure 4: Connection plot for exemplary instrument record.

This graph feature illustrates how instruments are linked to other scientific entities, revealing their role within the broader research ecosystem. However, it is limited when compared to the established knowledge graphs mentioned above.

¹⁴ About 10% of all DataCite instrument records have been registered at osf.io. For these entries, the frequency for specifying related identifiers is far above average, but these references are often incomplete in the DataCite record which made the data enrichment through the OSF API necessary.

Architecture for PID provider service integrations in a knowledge graph

The main issues here are the focus on a single central node and the processing of information exclusively from related identifiers. For this reason, we have created a Neo4J database containing instrument records from DataCite and B2INST. We are currently working on incorporating this database into our federated search tool to eliminate said limitations. Once this has been achieved, our prototype tool will offer many of the advantages of integrating instruments into well-established knowledge graphs, as well as some unique features.

However, to realize the full potential of PID-based knowledge graphs, quality metadata needs to specify the relations of the considered scientific resources comprehensively and consistently. For instruments, there is still the need to establish best practices. To this end, we wrote a report that gives guidance on how to connect instrument records with other research entities.¹⁵ The document is largely inspired by our work with the HZB as one of the PID4NFDI use case partners. It shows for the resources that most likely have a connection to an instrument (e.g., organizations, other instruments, datasets, publications, and samples) how related identifiers and relation types should be utilized with B2INST and DataCite, respectively. This includes target group specific advice on how to contribute to metadata that adequately represents the role of instruments in the scientific process.

Conclusion

The federated search tool serves as a dedicated discovery environment for instrument PIDs. It harmonizes metadata from DataCite and B2INST while retaining the specific qualities of each source. In doing so, it demonstrates how new PID types can be made visible and actionable. Having a single platform to find any instrument with a PID facilitates the attribution of instruments in scientific outputs and provides an entry point for assessing the current state and adoption of instrument PIDs. For those responsible for research data management and PID implementation, it offers a practical resource to monitor progress and identify areas for improvement.

While development of our tool is ongoing – most notably with regard to database integration for visualizing knowledge graphs – it can never entirely replicate the advantages that would come with a full integration of DataCite and B2INST

¹⁵ Böhm (2025).

Architecture for PID provider service integrations in a knowledge graph

instrument records into the PID Graph or the OpenAIRE Research Graph.

Large-scale platforms like these, with their wide user base, have the capacity to create broader awareness and to normalize instrument PIDs as a standard element of the PID landscape. Furthermore, such established systems typically have a solid sustainability plan for their services whereas the sustainability of our new prototype service is unclear. Finally, it makes good sense for established systems to consider a few more resource types, instead of developing individual systems for each resource type.

For these reasons, PID4NFDI continues to engage in dialogue with DataCite, OpenAIRE, and OpenAlex, including discussions on the representation of other emerging resource types for which PIDs are not yet fully established. Currently, the OpenAIRE Research Graph only indexes traditional research outputs, and most of these emerging resources do not fall into this category. However, among the options under consideration within OpenAIRE is the inclusion of infrastructures as a new category, which would be particularly suitable for integrating instruments and facilities.

References

- Böhm, J. (2025). Linking Instrument PIDs With Related Research Entities: Guidance Document. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535290>.
- De Castro, P., Herb, U., Rothfritz, L. & Schöpfel, J. (2023). Persistent Identifiers for Research Instruments and Facilities: An Emerging PID Domain in Need of Coordination. Bristol, UK: Knowledge Exchange. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7330372>.
- Demes, K., & Gould, M. (2025). DataCite Metadata Is Now Integrated in OpenAlex. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.5438/WE1X-2K68>.
- El-Gebali, S., & Böhm, J. (2025). Landscape Analysis of PID Practices in NFDI (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15689799>.
- Krahl, R., Darroch, L., Huber, R., Devaraju, A., Klump, J., Habermann, T., Stocker, M., & RDA PIDINST WG Members. (2022). Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00070>.
- Mayernik, M., Johnson, A., Julian, R., Murray, M., Mundoma, C., Ranganath, A., & Stossmeister, G. (2024). Persistent Identifiers for Instruments and Facilities: Current State, Challenges, and Opportunities. *Journal of eScience Librarianship*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.964>.
- OpenAlex. (2024). OpenAlex: End-to-end process for topic classification. <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bDopkhuGieQ4F8gGNj7sEc8WSE8mvLZS/edit#heading=h.5w2tb5fcg77r>.
- Springer, F. (2025). ePIC PIDs for Instruments in the Sensor Management System: Use Case Analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17733707>.
- Stathis, K., Ross, C., Vogt, S., & Siziva, K. (2024). Introducing DataCite Metadata Schema 4.5. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.5438/JVKK-8198>.
- Stocker, M., Darroch, L., Krahl, R., Habermann, T., Devaraju, A., Schwardmann, U., D'Onofrio, C. & Häggström, I. (2020). Persistent Identification of Instruments. *Data Science Journal*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-018>.